

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Paper

Evaluation of Acute and Subacute Toxicological Effects of Aqueous-Methanol Leaf Extract of *Luffa cylindrica* on Some Vital Organs of Wistar Rats

F. C. Nwinyi*¹, A. E. Ade-Oke², N. A. Sani³

^{1,2}Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Abuja, PMB 117, Abuja, Nigeria.

³Department of Veterinary Pathology, University of Abuja, PMB 117, Abuja, Nigeria.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 30 Jan. 2025

Keywords:

Luffa cylindrica, Toxicity, Organs, Gross pathology, Histopathology.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14771230

ABSTRACT

World Health Organization has advocated for countries to recognize the importance of medicinal plants for the treatment of several diseases and ailments. In fact, herbs and natural products are gaining significant attention in global world debate and many conventional medications have their origins in plants. *Luffa cylindrica* is a plant widely grown for industrial, medicinal, and culinary uses. Many cultures use various components of the plant, such as the fruit, leaves, and seeds, in their folk medicine in addition to its cosmetic uses. This research work was aimed at evaluating the acute and subacute toxicological effects of *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract on some organs in Wistar rats with the view of determining its safety considering its wide folkloric usage. In the acute toxicity study, rats were treated orally in biphasic manner with doses ranging from 10 mg/kg to 5000 mg/kg to determine the possible range of toxicity. In the subacute toxicity study, the rats were grouped into 4 (of five rats each). Rats in Group A were administered distilled water (10 ml/kg P.O) to serve as the negative control. Rats in groups B, C, D were treated with graded doses of the extract (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O) respectively. The treatment was done over a period of 28 days after which the rats were humanely sacrificed. Organs such as the heart, lungs, spleen, kidney and liver were excised for gross and histopathological studies. The acute toxicity study showed no mortality or signs of toxicity, even at doses as high as 5000 mg/kg P.O, indicating that the oral median lethal dose (LD50) is greater than 5000 mg/kg. This suggests that the extract is relatively safe. In the subacute toxicity study, the gross and histopathological examinations revealed no abnormalities in the organs.

*Corresponding Author: F. C. Nwinyi

Address: Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Abuja, PMB 117, Abuja, Nigeria.

Email : florence.nwinyi@uniabuja.edu.ng

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

These show that the integrity of the organs was not tampered with and further confirming the non-toxic nature of the *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract at the tested doses.

INTRODUCTION

Plants have long been used medicinally and much of modern medicine has its roots in the ancient practice of using plants for medicinal purposes, which predates human history. Debates about global health are paying a lot of attention to traditional herbal treatments because of their effectiveness, safety, and low side effect profile. They provide treatments for age-related illnesses that are not currently treated by modern medicine, such as immune disorders, amnesia, and osteoporosis¹. They are much sought after for primary healthcare in the developed world. Reports have shown that alternative medicines, such as decoctions made from plant stem bark, roots, and aerial parts, are used to cure a variety of ailments in rural Nigeria². Nevertheless, pharmacological and toxicological investigations are required to determine their potential therapeutic benefits and safety margin in relation to drug discovery. *Luffa cylindrica* is a tropical and subtropical vine that is a member of the Cucurbitaceae family and is often referred to as sponge gourd or loofah³. This plant, which is native to Asia and Africa, is widely grown for a variety of uses, including industrial, medicinal, and culinary^{4,5}. The dried fibrous skeleton of the fruit is also used as a loofah sponge, which is widely used in skincare routines to exfoliate dead skin cells and encourage blood circulation^{6,7}. Many cultures use various components of *Luffa cylindrica*, such as the fruits, leaves and seeds in their folk medicine. It is used in traditional medicine to treat ailments like diabetes, skin diseases, and jaundice^{8,9}. The fruit is used as a laxative, diuretic, and anti-inflammatory in Ayurveda^{4,10}. The plant is used for its analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties, which are useful in reducing pain and inflammation brought on by

a number of illnesses¹¹. Also, the seeds have long been utilized for their anthelmintic properties^{9,12,13}. Moreover, studies have shown that *Luffa cylindrica* extracts have antibacterial qualities, suggesting that they may be useful in the treatment of a variety of infections^{14,15}. Furthermore, *Luffa cylindrica* has demonstrated promise in the healing of wounds because of its antibacterial and anti-inflammatory qualities¹⁶. Hepato-protective qualities of *Luffa cylindrica* extracts have also been shown¹⁷. The plant's anticancer, antifungal, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties have all been linked to its rich and varied phytochemical content^{11,17,18,19,20}. Reports have revealed that *Luffa cylindrica* has been used medicinally for a long time, and its broad range of applications shows that it can be a useful therapeutic agent in both conventional and alternative medicine. The aim of the present study is to determine the safety margin for *Luffa cylindrica* considering its wide application and for possible drug development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Collection and Identification

Luffa cylindrica leaves were collected from University of Abuja Main Campus located at Giri, Gwagwalada Area Council of Abuja, Nigeria in the month of April, 2024. Gwagwalada has Latitude DMS: 8° 56' 29" N and Longitude DMS: 7° 5' 30" E. Identification and authentication of the samples were done by Mr. Akeem A. Lateef, a Plant Taxonomist with the Department of Medicinal Plants Research and Traditional Medicine (MPR & TM), National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development (NIPRD), Idu, Abuja, Nigeria. The specimen was identified to be of the family, Cucurbitaceae with Scientific name: *Luffa cylindrica*. Voucher specimen no: NIPRD/H/7727 was then assigned to the specimen.

Preparation of Crude Extract

The leaves of *Luffa cylindrica* were air-dried for a period of 14 days and was then pulverized with the aid of a milling machine. 660 g powdered leaves were extracted by maceration in 80 % methanol and stirred at different intervals for 24 h. The mixture was filtered using filter paper and the filtrate was concentrated using a water bath at 40 °C. The extract was then preserved in a refrigerator at 4 °C until required.

Determination of the Yield of the Extract

The percentage yield was calculated using the extracted concentrate weight in the given formula;

$$\text{Percentage yield of extract (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of extract}}{\text{Weight of pulverized L.C}} \times 100$$

Where L.C = *Luffa cylindrica*

Chemicals

The chemicals used for this research work include Methanol (Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany), Chloroform (Molychem^(R)-Mumbai) and Formaldehyde (G. KOEPCKE & CO, Hamburg, Germany).

Experimental Animals

Male Wistar rats weighing between 50 - 100 g purchased from University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria were used in this study. The rats were kept in well-ventilated cages under normal environmental conditions (12 h day and night cycles) in the Department of Veterinary Pharmacology and Toxicology, University of Abuja for three weeks to acclimatize and mature to desired weights of 100 - 150 g. They were fed with growers' mash (Chikun feeds[®] Nigeria, Ltd) and water *ad libitum*.

Ethical Approval

The approval for the research protocol was obtained from the University of Abuja Ethics Committee on Animal Use (UAECAU) with a reference number: UAECAU/2024/017. The study was carried out in line with the ethical protocol of ensuring that minimal number of animals were

used in the study. It also ensured that the animals were humanely handled.

Acute Toxicity Study (LD₅₀)

Acute toxicity study was carried out using the modified method of Lorke²¹. This experiment was aimed at calculating the oral median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract. The study was carried out in a biphasic manner. In the first phase, nine (9) male rats were randomly distributed into three groups (of 3 rats each) and graded doses of the plant leaf extract (10, 100, 1000 mg/kg) were administered orally to the various groups respectively. In the second phase, three groups (of two rats per group) were administered graded doses of 1600, 2900, 5000 mg/kg P.O of the extract following the observations of the rats in the first phase. The rats in both first and second phases were observed for changes in behaviour or toxicity signs and mortality for 72 h.

Subacute Toxicity Study

Wistar rats weighing between 100 – 150 g were used for the study. The rats were weighed and randomly allocated to four groups (Group A - D) with five rats in each group. The rats were marked using picric acid for identification in each group. Group A rats were given distilled water (10 ml/kg P.O) and served as negative control.

Group B rats were administered *Luffa cylindrica* extract (100 mg/kg P.O)

Group C rats were administered *Luffa cylindrica* extract (200 mg/kg P.O)

Group D rats were administered *Luffa cylindrica* extract (400 mg/kg P.O)

This treatment was carried out for 28 days during which rats were observed for toxicity signs and/or mortalities. The body weight of all the rats were also measured weekly to give room for adjustments in the quantity of the extract to be administered in relation to new weight possibly acquired by the experimental rats. The body weights were also taken at the end of the treatment

period before the rats were humanely sacrificed under chloroform anesthetic. Body organs such as the heart, lungs, spleen, kidney and liver were, thereafter, excised for the determination of the relative organ weights, gross examination of the organs, determination of the mean lesion index, determination of percentage severity of lesion, determination of percentage protection of the organs and histopathological examination of the organs.

Relative Organ Weight

The body organs (heart, spleen, lungs, kidney and liver) were excised, cleaned of any adhering tissues or fluids and weighed using a calibrated analytical balance. This was done for all the rats used for the subacute toxicity study. The relative organ weight for each of the organs was then calculated using the formular below:

$$\text{Relative Organ Weight} = \frac{\text{Organ Weight}}{\text{Body weight}} \times 100$$

Gross Examination of Organs

All the harvested organs (heart, lungs, spleen, kidney and liver) were grossly examined for any pathological change.

Standardized scoring system was adopted for quantifying the severity of observed abnormalities (if any) as follows:

Heart Scoring

The scoring for the heart was done according to the method of Lobetti ²².

- 0 = No visible lesions or abnormalities
- 1 = Slight hypertrophy or minor lesions
- 2 = Noticeable hypertrophy or multiple minor lesions
- 3 = Significant hypertrophy, necrosis, or extensive lesions

Lung Scoring

The scoring method of Boorman *et al* ²³ was adopted for scoring the lungs.

- 0 = No discoloration or lesions
- 1 = Slight discoloration or single small lesion
- 2 = Multiple lesions or moderate discoloration

- 3 = Extensive lesions or significant discoloration

Spleen Scoring

The scoring method of Suttie ²⁴ was used for the spleen.

- 0 = No enlargement or lesions
- 1 = Slight enlargement or single small nodule
- 2 = Moderate enlargement or multiple nodules
- 3 = Significant enlargement or extensive nodules

Kidney Scoring

The scoring method of Hard *et al* ²⁵ was adopted for the kidney.

- 0 = No lesions or abnormalities
- 1 = Slight discoloration or single small cyst
- 2 = Moderate discoloration or multiple cysts
- 3 = Significant discoloration, cysts, or necrosis

Liver Scoring

The scoring for the liver was done according to the method of Thoolen *et al* ²⁶

- 0 = No discoloration or lesions
- 1 = Slight discoloration or single small nodule
- 2 = Multiple nodules or moderate discoloration.
- 3 = Extensive nodules, significant discoloration, or necrosis

Determination of the Mean Lesion Index

The Mean Lesion Index for the organs was calculated using the formular:

$$\text{Mean Lesion Index} = \frac{\text{Total lesion indices in a group}}{\text{Total number of animals in the group}}$$

Determination of Percentage Severity of Lesion

The percentage severity of lesion on the organs was determined in the given formular:

$$\text{Percentage Severity of Lesion} = \frac{\text{Scores of lesions in a group}}{\text{Total lesion index of negative control group}} \times 100$$

Total lesion index of negative control group

Determination of Percentage Protection

The percentage protection of the organs was determined using the formular:

$$\text{Percentage Protection} = 100 - \% \text{ Severity of lesion}$$

Histopathological Examination of Organs

The excised organs were put in properly labelled sample bottles and were fixed in 10 % formalin. The fixed organs were embedded in wax to create

blocks which were then sectioned with Microtome to create tissue sections. The tissues were cleared of wax using Xylene and were stained with Haematoxylin and Eosin (H & E). The slides were then viewed under a binocular microscope (Omax®, China) at x 100 magnification for any histopathological change.

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean (SEM) and analyzed statistically by one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) as the case may be, using the International Business Machines Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (IBM SPSS) version 23 (Armonk, New York, USA), P values \leq 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Table 1: Determination of oral median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of aqueous-methanol extract of *Luffa cylindrica* leaves in rats.

Treatment	No of dead rats	No of rats alive
Phase 1		
<i>Luffa cylindrica</i>		
10 mg/kg P.O	0/3	3/3
100 mg/kg P.O	0/3	3/3
1000 mg/kg P.O	0/3	3/3
Phase 2		
<i>Luffa cylindrica</i>		
1600 mg/kg P.O	0/2	2/2
2900 mg/kg P.O	0/2	2/2
5000 mg/kg P.O	0/2	2/2

Subacute Toxicity Study

Mortality and Clinical Signs

No mortality was recorded and there was no visible clinical sign observed in all the rats throughout the 28 days treatment period.

Effect of *Luffa cylindrica* Leaf Extract on Relative Organ Weight of Rats Treated for 28 Days

The mean relative organ weights of the heart, spleen, kidney and liver of rats treated with *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O) for 28 days were inconsistent, having both

RESULTS

Extract Yield and Description

The weight of the pulverized *Luffa cylindrica* dried leaves was 660 g while the extract yield was 138.2 g. The percentage yield of the extract was then calculated to be 20.9 %. The extract obtained was dark-green in colour and slurry in consistency.

Acute Toxicity Study

No mortality or signs of toxicity were recorded 72 h after the treatment of rats with the aqueous-methanol extract of *Luffa cylindrica* leaves at doses ranging between 10 - 5000 mg/kg P.O. The oral median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of the extract was, therefore, estimated to be greater than 5000 mg/kg (Table 1).

reductions and increases in the values. The relative organ weights of the lungs decreased in a manner that was not dose-dependent. However, these variations in the relative weights of all the excised organs (heart, lungs, spleen, kidney and liver) were not significantly different from the relative organ weights of the negative control group (Table 2).

Table 2: Effect of aqueous-methanol extract of *Luffa cylindrica* leaves (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O) on relative organ weights of rats treated for 28 days.

Mean Relative Organ Weight (g) ± SEM					
Treatment	Heart	Lungs	Spleen	Kidney	Liver
Distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O	0.33 ± 0.02	0.87 ± 0.07	0.66 ± 0.09	0.68 ± 0.06 4.33 ± 0.16	4.33 ± 0.16
<i>Luffa cylindrica</i> 100 mg/kg P.O	0.32 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.04	0.41 ± 0.05	0.72 ± 0.03 4.30 ± 0.22	4.33 ± 0.16
200 mg/kg P.O	0.39 ± 0.03	0.77 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.11	0.78 ± 0.03 4.78 ± 0.16	4.78 ± 0.16
400 mg/kg P.O	0.35 ± 0.02	0.65 ± 0.08	0.47 ± 0.07	0.66 ± 0.06 4.03 ± 0.28	4.03 ± 0.28

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM; One way ANOVA; Tukey post hoc. *P ≤ 0.05 = significantly different from negative control group.

Gross Examination of Organs

The heart, lungs, spleen, kidney and liver appeared normal on gross examination. The hearts were normal in size, shape, consistency and colour and there were no signs of lesions or abnormal thickening (Plate 1). The lungs appeared pink with no evidence of lesions or fluid accumulation (Plate 2). The spleens were all elongated and dark red, with no signs of swelling or necrosis. The surface

was smooth without visible lesions (Plate 3). The kidneys appeared smooth, firm and reddish-brown in colour with no signs of lesions such as necrosis or cysts (Plate 4). The liver in all groups was of normal size with a smooth surface and dark reddish-brown colour. No signs of enlargement were observed (Plate 5). The scorings for severity of abnormalities on the organs were indicated in Table 3

Plate 1: Normal Gross observations of the Hearts of rats treated with distilled water (10 ml/kg P.O), aqueous-methanol leaf extract of *Luffa cylindrica* (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O): A = distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O, B = *Luffa cylindrica* 100 mg/kg P.O, C = *Luffa cylindrica* 200 mg/kg P.O, D = *Luffa cylindrica* 400 mg/kg P.O.

Plate 2: Normal Gross observations of the Lungs of rats treated with aqueous-methanol leaf extract of *Luffa cylindrica* (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O): A = distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O, B = *Luffa cylindrica* 100 mg/kg P.O, C = *Luffa cylindrica* 200 mg/kg P.O, D = *Luffa cylindrica* 400 mg/kg P.O.

Plate 3: Normal Gross observations of the Spleens of rats treated with distilled water (10 ml/kg P.O), aqueous-methanol leaf extract of *Luffa cylindrica* (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O): A = distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O, B = *L. cylindrica* 100 mg/kg P.O, C = *L. cylindrica* 200 mg/kg P.O, D = *L. cylindrica* 400 mg/kg P.O

Plate 4: Normal Gross observations of the Kidneys of rats treated with distilled water (10 ml/kg P.O), aqueous-methanol leaf extract of *Luffa cylindrica* (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O): A = distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O, B = *Luffa cylindrica* 100 mg/kg P.O, C = *Luffa cylindrica* 200 mg/kg P.O, D = *Luffa cylindrica* 400 mg/kg P.O

Plate 5: Normal Gross observations of the Livers of rats treated with distilled water (10 ml/kg P.O), aqueous-methanol leaf extract of *Luffa cylindrica* (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O): A = distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O, B = *Luffa cylindrica* 100 mg/kg P.O, C = *Luffa cylindrica* 200 mg/kg P.O, D = *Luffa cylindrica* 400 mg/kg P.O.

Table 3: Scoring for severity of lesions on the organs of rats treated for 28 days with aqueous-methanol extract of *Luffa cylindrica* leaves (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O)

Mean Scoring for severity of lesions on the organs					
Treatment	Heart	Lungs	Spleen	Kidney	Liver
Distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O.	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
<i>Luffa cylindrica</i> 100 mg/kg P.O.	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
200 mg/kg P.O.	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0
400 mg/kg P.O.	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM

Mean Lesion Score, Percentage Severity of Lesions and Percentage Protection of Organs

The calculated mean lesion score for all the organs (heart, lungs, spleen, kidney and liver) was zero, the percentage severity of lesion in all the organs

was calculated to be 0 % while the percentage protection for all the organs (heart, lungs, spleen, kidney and liver) was determined to be 100 % (Table 4).

Table 4: Mean lesion score, Percentage severity of lesions and Percentage Protection on Organs of rats treated for 28 days with aqueous-methanol extract of *Luffa cylindrica* leaves (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O)

Organ	Mean Lesion Score ± SEM	Percentage Severity of Lesions (%)	Percentage Protection (%)
Heart	0.0 ± 0.0	0	100
Lungs	0.0 ± 0.0	0	100
Spleen	0.0 ± 0.0	0	100

Kidney	0.0 ± 0.0	0	100
Liver	0.0 ± 0.0	0	100

The values of the mean lesion score are expressed as mean ± SEM

Histopathological Examination of Organs

Histological examination of the heart tissue revealed normal myocardial architecture with well-arranged cardiac muscle fibres and centrally located nuclei. No signs of necrosis or lesions were present (Plate 6). Spleen tissue revealed well-defined red and white pulp areas. The white pulp showed normal lymphoid follicles, and there were no signs of haemorrhage or necrosis (Plate 7).

Kidney histology revealed well-formed glomeruli with no signs of sclerosis. The renal tubules appeared normal, with no evidence of necrosis or interstitial inflammation (Plate 8). The liver showed normal hepatic lobular architecture with well-arranged hepatocytes and intact sinusoids. No signs of fibrosis or inflammatory cell infiltration were observed (Plate 9).

Plate 6: Normal Histopathological observations of the Hearts of rats treated with aqueous-methanol leaf extract of *Luffa cylindrica* (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O): A = distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O, B = *Luffa cylindrica* 100 mg/kg P.O, C = *Luffa cylindrica* 200 mg/kg P.O, D = *Luffa cylindrica* 400 mg/kg P.O.

Plate 7: Normal Histopathological observations of the Spleens of rats treated with aqueous-methanol leaf extract of *Luffa cylindrica* (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O): A = distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O, B = *Luffa cylindrica* 100 mg/kg P.O, C = *Luffa cylindrica* 200 mg/kg P.O, D = *Luffa cylindrica* 400 mg/kg P.O.

Plate 8: Normal Histopathological observations of the Kidneys of rats treated with aqueous-methanol leaf extract of *Luffa cylindrica* (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O): A = distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O, B = *Luffa cylindrica* 100 mg/kg P.O, C = *Luffa cylindrica* 200 mg/kg P.O, D = *Luffa cylindrica* 400 mg/kg P.O.

Plate 9: Normal Histopathological observations of the Livers of rats treated with aqueous-methanol leaf extract of *Luffa cylindrica* (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O): A = distilled water 10 ml/kg P.O, B = *Luffa cylindrica* 100 mg/kg P.O, C = *Luffa cylindrica* 200 mg/kg P.O, D = *Luffa cylindrica* 400 mg/kg P.O.

DISCUSSION

The present study evaluated the acute and subacute toxicological effects of *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O) in Wistar rats. The acute toxicity study demonstrated that no mortality or signs of toxicity were observed in rats administered *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract at doses ranging from 10 mg/kg to 5000 mg/kg P.O. This indicates that the oral median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of the extract is greater than 5000 mg/kg. According

to Lorke²¹, any substance that has an oral median lethal dose greater than 1000 mg/kg is relatively non-toxic and is safe for consumption. This suggests that *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract possibly has a high margin of safety, having an oral median lethal dose greater than 5000 mg/kg. This is consistent with the findings of Jain *et al*¹⁴, who reported that many plant extracts used in traditional medicine exhibit low acute toxicity when administered within certain dosage ranges.

Similarly, studies by Kumar and Bhattacharya⁶ found no acute toxicity for extracts containing phytochemicals like flavonoids and saponins, which are also present in *Luffa cylindrica*. Subacute toxicity studies are usually carried out to assess the possible side effects of a novel medication after two to four weeks of administration. Subacute toxicity studies are also carried out as range-finding studies to choose dosage ranges for use in later sub-chronic and chronic toxicity studies. Additionally, preliminary clinical trials with a maximum treatment length of three days may be supported by subacute toxicity investigations. Although the purpose of these studies is to evaluate the development and remission of lesions caused by drugs, they are typically too short in duration to detect all potential side effects that can occur during long-term clinical usage or during ongoing toxicity and carcinogenicity testing^{27, 28}. In the present subacute toxicity study, no mortality or visible clinical signs were observed over the 28-day treatment period with *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O). The absence of adverse effects such as lethargy or abnormal behaviours, supports the relative safety of *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract. These results also corroborate findings from previous studies, such as those by Ali *et al*¹⁷, which demonstrated the non-toxic nature of *Luffa cylindrica* extracts over extended periods of administration. The lack of clinical signs or toxicity is in contrast with some reports on other medicinal plants, where long-term use has been associated with potential organ toxicity²⁹. In addition, the present study showed that the leaf extract of *Luffa cylindrica* did not cause any gross or histopathological changes in vital organs such as the heart, lungs, spleen, kidney and liver after the 28 days treatment at doses of 100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O. It demonstrated high percentage of protection (100 %) for all major organs and these observations further confirm the

safety of *Luffa cylindrica* at the tested doses. These results are in line with the work of Singh *et al*,³⁰ who reported the hepatoprotective and antioxidant properties of *Luffa cylindrica*, emphasizing its minimal toxicity when used in appropriate doses.

Generally, studies that found adverse effects with prolonged use of herbal extracts emphasize the importance of dose and duration in herbal medicine safety³¹. In the present study, the absence of organ toxicity at the tested oral doses of 100, 200 and 400 mg/kg generally supports further investigation of *Luffa cylindrica* for broader pharmacological applications at these evaluated dose ranges.

CONCLUSION

The aqueous-methanol extract of *Luffa cylindrica* leaves (100, 200 and 400 mg/kg P.O) demonstrated a high safety profile in Wistar rats treated for 28 days. The acute toxicity study showed no mortality or signs of toxicity, even at doses as high as 5000 mg/kg P.O, indicating that the oral median lethal dose (LD₅₀) is greater than 5000 mg/kg, thus, suggesting that *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract is relatively safe. In the subacute toxicity study, no adverse effects on organ health observed after 28 days of treatment further confirm the non-toxic nature of the extract. *Luffa cylindrica* leaf extract is, therefore, relatively safe for treatment of many diseases for which it is traditionally indicated. However, further studies should involve evaluation with doses above 400 mg/kg P.O. Sub-chronic and chronic toxicity studies would also be valuable for further insights regarding the safety margin of *Luffa cylindrica* leaves when used as medicine.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Our sincere gratitude goes to Mr. David O. Akumka and Mr. Adamu Muhammed who are the Academic Technologists with the Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Abuja, Nigeria

for their efforts and contributions toward the success of this research work.

REFERENCES

1. Ved D. K. and Goraya G. S.: Demand and supply of medicinal plants in India. NMP 2000.
2. Nwaehujor C.O., Igile G.O, Ode J.O and Udegbunam R.I: Anti-inflammatory activities of methanol leaf extract of *Bridelia micrantha* (Hochst) Baill. (Euphorbiceae) in Wistar rats *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science* (2014), vol. 4(06), pp. 068-073.
3. Wang H., Liu Y. and Zhang J: *Luffa cylindrica*: Botany, ethnobotany, and medicinal uses. *Plants* (2023), 12(6), 905.
4. Gupta S., Sharma A. K. and Gupta A. P: *Luffa cylindrica*: An important medicinal plant. *International Journal of Research in Ayurveda and Pharmacy* (2011), 2(2), 451–456.
5. Chung H. Y., Yoon S. H., and Lee K. J: *Luffa cylindrica*: A comprehensive review of its cultivation and applications. *Horticulture Research* (2023), 10(1), 45-58.
6. Kumar A. and Bhattacharya D: *Luffa cylindrica*: An overview. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research* (2013), 20(2), 28–32.
7. Srinivasan K., Reddy S. and Kaur S: The use of *Luffa cylindrica* loofah in dermatological applications: Benefits and efficacy. *Skin Health and Disease* (2024), 5(2), 104-115. <https://doi.org/10.1002/shd2.153>
8. Panda S., Mohanta Y. K., Padhi L. and Mohanta T. K: A review on pharmacological and phytochemical aspects of *Luffa acutangula*. *Pharmacology online* (2011), 3, 582-591.
9. Singh A. and Patel R: Environmental impact on the phytochemical composition of medicinal plants: A study on *Luffa cylindrica*. *Plant Research Journal* (2023), 10(2), 45-57.
10. Patel A. and Gupta R: Ayurvedic uses of *Luffa cylindrica*: A review of its therapeutic potential. *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge* (2022), 21(3), 654-668. <https://doi.org/10.55845/ijtk.21.3.654>
11. Kumar P., Kumar R. and Sharma R: A review on phytochemical and pharmacological aspect of *Luffa cylindrica*. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research* (2020), 13(3), 17-21.
12. Kirtikar K. R. and Basu B. D: *Indian Medicinal Plants* (Vol. 3). International Book Distributors (2001).
13. Ali H., Khan M. and Hussain F: Anthelmintic potential of medicinal plants: A review on *Luffa cylindrica*. *Journal of Parasitology Research* (2021), 29(3), 145-153.
14. Jain V., Pareek A. and Jain S: Antibacterial activity of aqueous and alcoholic extracts of *Luffa cylindrica* fruits. *Pharmacologyonline* (2012), 2, 1168–1172
15. Eddy A. O., Olowofeso I. O., Olajide O., Ajayi I. O. and Ayinde A. S: Antimicrobial properties of *Luffa cylindrica* extracts. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research* (2023), 17(3), 119-127.
16. Goyal B. R., Goyal R. K. and Mehta A. A.: Phyto-pharmacology of *Luffa cylindrica*. *Pharmacognosy Reviews* (2009), 3(5), 344-349.
17. Ali M. S., Islam M. T., Rahman M. M., Khanam J. A. and Sadik G: Hepatoprotective activity of *Luffa cylindrica* fruits. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science* (2015), 5(03), 124-128.
18. Suresh K., Dharani P., Prabhakaran K. and Manian S: Phytochemical investigation on the seeds of *Luffa cylindrica* (L.) M. Roem. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research* (2012), 6(1), 62-64.
19. Zhang H., Wu Z. and Li P: Antifungal properties of bioactive saponins in *Luffa*

- cylindrica seeds. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research* (2022), 18(5), 33-45.
20. Patel R. and Singh D: Phytochemical diversity and potential uses of *Luffa cylindrica* in modern medicine. *International Journal of Phytotherapy* (2023), 15(4), 98-114.
21. Lorke D: A new approach to practical acute toxicity testing. *Archives of Toxicology* (1983), 54(4), 275-287.
22. Lobetti R. G: Prevalence, classification, and severity of cardiac changes in chronic renal failure. *Journal of Veterinary Internal Medicine* (2000), 14(5), 462-468.
23. Boorman G. A., Eustis S. L., Elwell M. R., Montgomery C. A. and MacKenzie W. F.: *Pathology of the Fischer Rat: Reference and atlas*. Academic Press (1984).
24. Suttie A. W: Histopathology of the spleen. *Toxicologic Pathology* (2006), 34(5), 466-503. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01926230600868138>
25. Hard G. C., Johnson K. J., Cohen S. M. and Hish, G. A.: *A comprehensive toxicological pathology guide*. *Toxicological Pathology* (2008), 33(1), 123-128.
26. Thoolen B., Maronpot R. R., Harada T., Nyska A., Rousseaux C., Nolte T. ... and Rittinghausen S: Proliferative and non-proliferative lesions of the rat and mouse hepatobiliary system. *Toxicologic Pathology* (2010), 38(7S), 5S-81S.
27. Colerangle J. B: Subacute toxicity. *Encyclopedia of Toxicology* (3rd edition, pp. 499-501). Academic Press (2013).
28. Jansen K., Hargrove C. and Phillips E: Subacute toxicity studies: Importance, methodology, and limitations. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology* (2024), 413, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2023.115246>
29. Dunnick J.K. and Nyska A. (2013). The toxicity and pathology of selected dietary herbal medicines. *Toxicologic Pathology*, 41(2), 374-386.
30. Singh A., Handa S. S. and Sharma A: Hepatoprotective activity of ethanolic extract of *Luffa cylindrica*. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* (2010), 72(4), 532-534.
31. McClean E., Cogswell M. and Egli I: Global burden of anaemia: A comprehensive review. *Haematological Reports* (2022), 20(3), 165-174.

HOW TO CITE: F. C. Nwinyi*, A. E. Ade-Oke, N. A. Sani, Evaluation of Acute and Subacute Toxicological Effects of Aqueous-Methanol Leaf Extract of *Luffa cylindrica* on Some Vital Organs of Wistar Rats, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 1, 2491-2503 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14771230>

